

**LEVEL OF INTEGRATION OF VALUES EDUCATION
IN CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION: BASIS FOR
PROGRAM PLAN**

by

**Lourdes B. Avila
Salvador U. Barros II**

**Polytechnic University of the Philippines
Lopez Quezon**

Abstract – This study examined how values education is integrated into classroom instruction and how it relates to students' character development. It focused on three key areas of classroom practice: lesson planning and content delivery, teaching strategies and methods, and classroom management and discipline. At the same time, students' character development was observed in terms of respect and empathy, responsibility and discipline, and honesty and integrity. A descriptive-correlational design was used, with data gathered through survey questionnaires and supported by observation of classroom behaviors.

The findings showed that values education is generally integrated in classroom instruction. Among the areas assessed, teachers were most consistent in designing activities that promote good character and in encouraging reflective discussions on moral issues. Positive behavior was also reinforced through recognition and classroom routines that support respect and fairness. Students showed strong expressions of care for others, punctuality, and truthfulness, although some aspects such as consistent use of respectful language and admission of mistakes were observed at a slightly lower level.

It was found out that a strong and significant relationship between the integration of values education and students' character development ($r = 0.81, p < 0.05$). This suggests that when values are meaningfully embedded in instruction, students are more likely to demonstrate positive attitudes and behaviors. Based on these results, the study proposes the development of a program plan aimed at strengthening the integration of values education in classroom practices to support both academic learning and character formation.

Keywords: Values education, Classroom instruction, program plan, integration,

INTRODUCTION

Education is not only concerned with developing learners' academic abilities but also with shaping their character and guiding their behavior. In today's rapidly changing society, schools are expected to play a crucial role in nurturing values such as respect, responsibility, honesty, and empathy among students. These values help learners become not just knowledgeable individuals, but also responsible members of the community.

Values education becomes more meaningful when it is not treated as a separate subject, but instead is woven into everyday teaching practices. Through classroom instruction, teachers have the

opportunity to model and integrate positive values across different learning areas. The way lessons are delivered, the interactions within the classroom, and the activities designed for students all contribute to the development of their attitudes and moral perspectives.

However, the extent to which values education is integrated into classroom instruction may vary depending on teaching approaches, available resources, and institutional priorities. Some educators may consistently embed values in their lessons, while others may find it challenging to do so due to time constraints or lack of clear guidelines. This variation highlights the need to examine how values education is currently practiced in the classroom setting.

The study focused on determining the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction. The findings of this study aim was to provide a clearer understanding of current practices and identify areas that may need improvement. Ultimately, the results served as a basis for developing a program plan that can strengthen the integration of values education and support teachers in fostering holistic student development.

Background of the Study

Teachers hold a central role in making values education visible and meaningful. Their approach to instruction, the examples they provide, and the way they manage classroom situations all contribute to how students understand and practice values. However, the extent to which values are integrated may differ from one classroom to another. Some teachers may consciously include values in their lessons, while others may focus more on content delivery due to time constraints, curriculum requirements, or lack of structured guidance. This variation raised questions about how consistently values education is being incorporated into everyday teaching practices.

Identifying current practices in classroom helped determine areas that needed support and improvement. The findings was used as a foundation for designing a program plan that will guide teachers in strengthening the integration of values in their lessons. By doing so, schools/university's can better ensure that college students are not only academically prepared but are also equipped with the values needed to become responsible members of society.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Recent studies emphasized the importance of integrating values education into classroom instruction as part of holistic student development. According to Arvanitis and Kalliris (2020), moral integrity and consistency in teaching practices are essential in strengthening students' value formation. Their study highlights that when teachers consistently model ethical behavior and integrated moral lessons into instruction, students are more likely to develop self-regulation and positive social behavior.

Similarly, Van Brummelen and Lin (2020) found that integrating values-based discussions into classroom activities enhanced student engagement and encourages reflection on ethical issues. Their study showed that teachers who embed values in subject matter instruction created more meaningful learning experiences, especially when students are given opportunities to connect lessons with real-life situations. This supported the idea that values education is most effective when it is not treated as a separate subject but integrated across learning areas.

In a related study, Mara (2025) examined how teachers integrate moral values in classroom management and found that establishing clear rules, modeling respectful behavior, and reinforcing discipline contributed significantly to student character development. The study further revealed that values integration helped reduce behavioral problems and promotes a more positive classroom environment, where students are more likely to practice respect and responsibility.

Likewise, Naquines et al. (2025) highlighted that teachers' positive perceptions of values integration in science instruction lead to improved student discipline, cooperation, and ethical awareness. Their findings showed that contextualized teaching strategies, such as using real-life examples and collaborative learning, strengthen the internalization of values among learners.

Moreover, Guerrero and Estera (2025) reported that consistent teaching of values education significantly influences students' classroom behavior. Their study revealed that when values such as honesty, responsibility, and respect are consistently reinforced, students demonstrate improved behavior and stronger moral decision-making skills.

Overall, the reviewed studies consistently reveal that the integration of values education in classroom instruction plays a crucial role in shaping students' character. Teachers' instructional practices, classroom management strategies, and use of value-based activities are key factors that influence how effectively students develop positive values and behavior.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction as a basis for developing a school-based program plan.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction in terms of:
 - 1.1 lesson planning and content delivery
 - 1.2 teaching strategies and methods
 - 1.3 instructional management and discipline
2. What is the level of students' observed character development in terms of:
 - 2.1 respect and empathy
 - 2.2 responsibility and discipline
 - 2.3 honesty and integrity
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction, and the level of students' observed character development?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what program plan may be proposed to strengthen the values education integration in the classroom?

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored with the Character Education Theory developed by Lickona (1991), which underscores the role of schools in fostering moral and ethical development. This theory supported the intentional inclusion of core values in all aspects of teaching and learning. It emphasized that values should be consistently practiced, reinforced, and integrated into daily instruction rather than treated as separate or isolated lessons. Guided by these theoretical perspectives, the study

examined how values education is integrated into classroom instruction and used the findings as a basis for developing a program plan that can strengthen values formation among students.

Hypothesis

The hypothesis that was tested using 0.05 level of significance was that there is no significant relationship between the level of character education integration in classroom instruction and students' character development.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction in Polytechnic University of the Philippines in Lopez, Quezon during the school year 2023-2024 as a basis for developing a school-based program plan. The researcher described the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction in terms of lesson planning and content delivery, teaching strategies and methods, and instructional management and discipline. On the other hand, the researcher also described the level of students' observed character development in terms of respect and empathy, responsibility and discipline, and honesty and integrity. Based on the findings of the study, a program plan was proposed to strengthen the values education integration in the classroom. The period of study was conducted from October, 2023 to January, 2024.

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive correlational research to describe the relationship between the level of character education integration in classroom instruction and students' character development.

Locale and Population

The setting of the study was at Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Lopez branch in Quezon, Philippines. The respondents involved 50 teachers from the different departments of the university.

Research Instruments

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was designed to measure the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction. It consisted of statements describing teaching practices, classroom activities, and teacher-student interactions where values may be incorporated. The respondents rated each item in the questionnaire using a 4-point Likert scale to indicate how often these practices were observed or implemented. The instrument was divided into sections to capture different dimensions such as lesson planning and content delivery, teaching strategies and methods, and instructional management and discipline.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. Level of integration of values education in classroom instruction

1.1 Lesson Planning and Content Delivery. Table 1 showed the level of implementation of character education in classroom instruction in terms of lesson planning and content delivery.

Table 1
Level of Integration of Value Education in terms of Lesson Planning and Content Delivery

Indicators	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Integrated moral and ethical values into the objectives of each lesson plan	3.14	Integrate
Designed learning activities that highlighted good character and citizenship	3.53	Fully integrate
Incorporated real-life examples that reflected honesty, respect, and responsibility.	3.48	Integrate
Aligned lesson content with the school’s core values and character education goals.	3.15	Integrate
Over-all Mean	3.32	Integrate

Data revealed that teachers fully integrated design learning activities that highlighted good character and citizenship with a mean of 3.53, followed immediately in incorporating real-life examples that reflected honesty, respect, and responsibility as described from the mean of 3.48, and that the teachers integrate moral and ethical values into the objectives of each lesson plan with a mean of 3.14.

According to Lee and Kim (2021) aligned lesson content with a school’s core values and character education goals strengthens both academic achievement and personal development by embedding ethical and social principles into learning experiences. In his study Lee and Kim (2021) revealed that integrating values such as respect, responsibility, and empathy into classroom instruction improved students’ motivation, social skills, and emotional regulation. The research highlights that consistent alignment of lessons with value education fostered a positive school climate, encouraged student engagement, and reinforced pro-social behavior.

1.2 Teaching Strategies and Methods. Table 2 showed the level of implementation of character education in classroom instruction in terms of teaching strategies and methods.

Table 2
Level of Integration of Value Education in terms of Teaching Strategies and Methods

Indicators	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Applied cooperative learning to promote teamwork and empathy among students	3.47	Integrate

Utilized storytelling or case studies that demonstrated moral decision-making	3.14	Integrate
Encouraged reflective discussions on ethical dilemmas and moral lessons	3.51	Fully integrate
Integrated value-laden activities in classroom instruction to reinforce good behavior	3.12	Integrate
Employed role-playing or simulations to help students practice moral reasoning	3.45	Integrate
Over-all Mean	3.33	Integrate

It was found out that the teachers fully integrated reflective discussions on ethical dilemmas and moral lessons with a mean of 3.51, followed immediately integrated cooperative learning to promote teamwork and empathy among students as seen from the mean of 3.47, and that the teachers integrate value-laden activities in classroom instruction to reinforce good behavior as indicated from the mean of 3.14.

Data confirmed the study of Johnson and Johnson (2020) that applying cooperative learning to promote teamwork and empathy among students enhanced both social and academic development by engaging learners in structured collaborative activities. It was found out that when students participated in cooperative learning groups, they exhibit higher levels of interpersonal skills, including empathy, communication, and conflict resolution, while simultaneously improving academic performance.

1.3 Classroom Management and Discipline. Table 3 showed the level of implementation of character education in classroom instruction in terms of classroom management and discipline.

Table 3
Level of Integration of Value Education in terms of Instructional Management and Discipline

Indicators	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Established clear rules and expectations that reflected respect and fairness	3.36	Integrate
Modeled ethical behavior when handling classroom conflicts or misconduct.	3.11	Integrate
Reinforced positive behavior through recognition and encouragement.	3.52	Fully integrate
Addressed misbehavior in a way that teaches accountability and empathy.	3.24	Integrate
Maintained a classroom environment that promotes mutual respect and discipline.	3.38	Integrate
Over-all Mean	3.32	Integrate

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It was found out that the teachers fully integrated reinforcing positive behavior through recognition and encouragement as seen from the mean 3.52, followed immediately that they integrated maintaining a classroom environment that promoted mutual respect and discipline as indicated from the mean of 3.38, and that the teachers integrated modeling ethical behavior when handled classroom conflicts or misconduct as described from the mean of 3.11.

The study confirmed the study of Wang and Sun (2021) that classrooms with explicitly communicated, consistent, and fair rules experienced lower levels of disruptive behavior and higher student engagement. The research highlighted that when students understand behavioral expectations grounded in respect and equity, they are more likely to internalize these values, demonstrate self-regulation, and engage in pro-social interactions. Established clear rules and expectations that reflected respect and fairness promoted a positive classroom environment and supports students' social and moral development

Problem 2. Level of Students' Observed Character Development

2.1 Respect and Empathy. Table 4 showed the level of students' observed character development in terms of respect and empathy.

Table 4
Level of Students' Observed Character Development
in terms of Respect and Empathy

Indicators	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Showed politeness and courtesy toward teachers and classmates	3.47	Observed
Listen attentively and consider others' perspectives during discussions	3.14	Observed
Demonstrate care for peers who are in need	3.51	Fully observed
Used respectful language in both face-to-face and communication	3.12	Observed
Appreciated and accepted differences in opinions, beliefs, and backgrounds	3.45	Observed
Over-all Mean	3.34	Observed

Data revealed that teachers have assessed that their students fully observed demonstrating care and concern for peers who are in need with a mean of 3.51, followed immediately that the students were observed showing politeness and courtesy toward teachers and classmates based

from the mean of 3.47, and that the teachers rated that their students observed use respectful language in both face-to-face and online communication with a mean of 3.12.

Demonstrated politeness and courtesy toward teachers and classmates promoted a respectful and collaborative learning environment that supported both social and academic growth. A study by Chen (2021) found that students who consistently practiced courteous behaviors, such as active listening, respectful language, and consideration of others’ opinions, exhibited stronger peer relationships, improved classroom engagement, and reduced conflict. Integrated these practices into daily classroom routines cultivated a positive school climate, encouraged mutual respect, and enhanced students’ overall interpersonal and academic development.

2.2 Responsibility and Discipline. Table 5 showed the level of students’ observed character development in terms of responsibility and discipline.

Table 5
Level of Students’ Observed Character Development
in terms of Responsibility and Discipline

Indicators	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Completed assigned tasks and projects with minimal supervision	3.36	Observed
Followed school and classroom rules consistently	3.27	Observed
Exhibited punctuality and preparedness in all class activities	3.51	Fully observed
Took responsibility for actions and decisions made	3.42	Observed
Displayed self-control and patience when faced with challenges	3.34	Observed
Over-all Mean	3.38	Observed

Findings indicated that the teachers assessed that the students fully observed exhibiting punctuality and preparedness in all class activities with a mean of 3.51, followed immediately that the students have observed in taking responsibility for actions and decisions made with a mean of 3.12, and that the students were observed to display self-control and patience when faced with challenges based from the mean of 3.34.

Encouraged students to take responsibility for their actions and decisions fostered accountability, self-regulation, and personal growth within the learning environment. A study by García and Torres (2022) found that when students were guided to reflect on their choices and understand the consequences of their behavior, they developed stronger decision-making skills, higher self-discipline, and improved academic engagement. Embedded these practices into classroom routines cultivated a culture of accountability, promote responsible behavior, and support students’ holistic development as conscientious and self-aware individuals.

2.3 Honesty and Integrity. Table 6 showed the level of students' observed character development in terms of honesty and integrity.

Table 6
Level of Students' Observed Character Development
in terms of Honesty and Integrity

Indicators	Mean	Verbal interpretation
Told the truth even when consequences are unfavorable	3.52	Fully observed
Submitted only original work and avoid dishonest academic practices	3.25	Observed
Admitted mistakes and make efforts to correct them	3.18	Observed
Honored agreements and keep promises made to others	3.13	Observed
Demonstrated sincerity and fairness in dealing with classmates and teachers	3.49	Observed
Over-all Mean	3.31	Observed

It was found out that the teachers have fully observed that the students tell the truth even when consequences were unfavorable with a mean of 3.52, followed immediately that the students were observed to demonstrate sincerity and fairness in dealing with classmates and teachers as seen from the mean of 3.49 and that the students have observed to honor agreements and keep promises made to others based from the mean of 3.13.

Encouraged students to submit only original work and avoid dishonest academic practices promotes integrity, personal accountability, and ethical scholarship. A study by Smith and Al-Khatib (2021) found that when teachers explicitly taught the importance of academic honesty and reinforced strategies for producing original work, students demonstrated higher levels of responsibility, critical thinking, and ethical decision-making. Incorporated these practices into classroom routines can strengthen students' moral development, enhanced the credibility of academic outcomes, and cultivated lifelong habits of honesty and ethical conduct.

Problem 3. Significant relationship between the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction, and the level of students’ observed character development

Table 7
Significant relationship between the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction, and the level of students’ observed character development

Variables	Pearson’s r	Correlation	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Level of integration of values education	0.81	High correlation	0.001	Reject	Significant
Level of students’ observed character development					

Based on the results of Pearson’s r of 0.81, it can be said that there is a high correlation between the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction, and the level of students’ observed character development. Furthermore, the hypothesis was rejected and concluded that was significant relationship between the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction, and the level of 0.001 was less than 0.05.

Findings revealed that there is a meaningful connection between how much values education is incorporated into teaching and how students develop their character. When values such as honesty, respect, and responsibility are consistently included in lessons and classroom activities, students are more likely to show positive behaviors and attitudes. In other words, the stronger the integration of values education in instruction, the more noticeable the improvement in students’ character development.

Problem 4. Proposed Program plan to strengthen the values education integration in the classroom

Based on the findings of the study, a program plan was designed to improve how values education is carried out in the classroom by helping teachers strengthen their skills in planning lessons, choosing effective strategies, and managing learning environments. This can be done through trainings, shared planning sessions, and the use of instructional materials that naturally incorporate values. The program plan highlights the importance of using differentiated approaches to help students better understand and practice values such as honesty, respect, responsibility, and empathy.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The level of integration of values education in classroom instruction is integrated across lesson planning and content delivery, teaching strategies and methods, and instructional management and discipline.

2. The level of students' observed character development in terms of respect, empathy, responsibility, discipline, honesty, and integrity is generally evident in classroom behavior, with stronger manifestation in care for others, punctuality, and truthfulness.

3. Significant relationship existed between the level of integration of values education in classroom instruction, and the level of students' observed character development.

4. A program plan was developed to enhance the character development of the students.

Recommendations

Based from the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Teachers may strengthen and consistently integrate values education across lesson planning, teaching strategies, and classroom management to ensure deeper and more uniform integration in classroom instruction.

2. School administrators may continue to reinforce and sustain character development programs that promote respect, empathy, responsibility, discipline, honesty, and integrity through value-based activities to further enhance students' positive behavior.

3. Strengthen the integration of values education in classroom instruction to enhance students' character development.

4. Consider the program plan developed to further enhance and sustain students' character development through strengthened values education integration in classroom instruction.

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